

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF 3-D WOVEN CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A newly patented process for 3-D weaving of preforms is presented. Geometrical structures of composites made with 3-D woven carbon fiber preforms and epoxy matrix were studied. A new method for predicting detailed structural parameters of 3-D orthogonal woven preforms and their composites has been developed. Relationship between structural properties and process parameters is given. A finite element model was developed and used to predict the tensile moduli of the 3-D orthogonal woven carbon/epoxy composites. Predicted and measured properties are compared.

Keywords: 3-D weaving, 3-D woven composites, textile preforms, textile composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional woven structural composites offer advantages such as the capability of forming 3-D net shapes and improved composite properties, especially with regard to damage tolerance. The process for manufacturing 3-D woven preforms can be computerized and automated to produce preforms uniformly and economically, and therefore, improve the reliability of the composites. Because of these advantages, 3-D woven structural composites show a good potential for a broad range of applications.

It has been shown by several publications that the properties of advanced textile composites depend to a great extent on the fiber architecture. By adding the fiber reinforcement in the thickness direction, 3-D woven composites eliminate the delamination which is a major drawback for 2-D composites. However, this is usually at the expense of the in-plane tensile strength and other properties. No one fiber architecture can meet the demands of every end use. Volume fractions of fiber and dimensions of microstructure of composites play important roles in determining structural and mechanical properties of 3-D woven composites. Methods for predicting volume fractions of fiber and dimensions of micro structure are needed for preform and composite design and for structural and mechanical analysis. Mohamed et al [1] developed a method for predicting several geometrical parameters of 3-D orthogonal woven preforms, such as fiber volume fractions in each direction, the warp spacing, weft spacing, and Z yarn spacing. However, some of the microstructural dimensions, which are important for micro-mechanical modeling and fabric design, are not determined.

The purpose of this study is to develop a new method for predicting detailed structural parameters of 3-D orthogonal woven preforms and their composites to form a basis for fabric design and micro-mechanical modeling of composites.

2. THE NEW 3-D WEAVING MACHINE

A newly patented 3-D automated weaving machine developed at the College of Textiles and the Mars Mission Research Center of North Carolina State University has been described by Mohamed et al [1,2,3]. The 3-D weaving machine is computer controlled. Warp yarns taken from bobbins on a creel are separated into layers forming the fixed open warp sheds to allow for weft insertion. Multiple weft yarns are inserted through the sheds by needles. The weft yarn loops are temporarily held on the opposite side by a vertical "selvage needle". The insertion needles are then withdrawn to their original position leaving behind a set of doubled weft yarns. A reed is brought forward (beat-up) packing the yarns into a tight structure. While the reed is forward, the harness are crossed thus placing the Z yarns, which are fed into the machine parallel with warp yarns and separated into two layers controlled by harness, into the woven structure and a vertical component is added. The selvage needle is lowered and the formed structure is then "taken-up", that is, moved a distance corresponding to the required spacing of the weft yarns. The reed is then moved back and the entire cycle is repeated.

3. STRUCTURE OF 3-D WOVEN PREFORMS AND THEIR COMPOSITES

Based on the system used for controlling the Z yarns (vertical yarns), the structure could be either 3-D orthogonal, angle interlock, warp interlock or combination of all three in the same piece. Thick panels and structural elements with different cross sections such as T, I and double stiffened panels with fairly thick walls in all directions were produced on the automated machine mentioned above. A typical structure of 3-D orthogonal woven fabric is shown by Figure 1.

Figure 1. A typical structure of 3-D orthogonal woven fabric.

The fiber volume fraction in a unit cell can be calculated as follows [1]:

$$V'_f = \frac{S_w d_z + S_f d_w + S_z d_f}{d_w d_f d_z} \times 100\% = \left(\frac{S_w}{d_w d_f} + \frac{S_f}{d_f d_z} + \frac{S_z}{d_w d_z} \right) \times 100\% = C'_w + C'_f + C'_z \quad (1)$$

where

S_w , S_f , and S_z are the cross-sectional areas of fiber in the directions of warp, weft, and Z in a unit cell; d_w , d_f , and d_z are the dimensions defining a unit cell as shown in Figure 2; and C'_w , C'_f , and C'_z are the fiber volume fractions in the directions of warp, weft, and Z in a unit cell.

However, as it can be seen in Figure 2 that the number of the weft layers is one more than that of warp layers, that is, if there are n layers of warps, then the number of weft layers will be $n+1$, therefore, Equation (1) need to be modified for calculation of the total fiber volume fraction of the entire fabric.

For a 3-D orthogonal woven fabric panel with a rectangular cross section and of n layers of warp, the total thickness t of the fabric can be expressed as:

$$t = nd_f + F_z + 2h \quad (2)$$

where d_f is the height of a unit cell; F_z is the height of the weft fiber bundle; and h is thickness of Z yarn segments which pass over the top and bottom surfaces as shown in Figure 2.

Equation (2) is based on the following assumptions:

- 1) the yarns in the fabric remain straight in all three directions;
- 2) the yarn size in each direction was kept the same;
- 3) the structure is uniform.

In Equation (2), h is unknown. From the observation of many cross-sectional micrographs of 3-D woven composites, it was found that the thicknesses of Z yarn segments which pass over both surfaces are fairly thin. As an approximation, h can be considered as zero.

Then, total fiber volume fraction V_f of fabric can be calculated as:

$$V_f = C_w + C_f + C_z = \frac{nS_w}{td_w} + \frac{(n+1)S_f}{td_z} + \frac{S_z}{d_w d_z} \quad (3)$$

where $C_w = (nS_w)/(td_w)$, $C_f = (n+1)S_f/(td_z)$, and $C_z = S_z/(d_w d_z)$ are the fiber volume fractions of fabric in the directions of warp, weft, and Z respectively.

To carry out the calculations for total fiber volume fraction V_f and fabric thickness t , all dimensions defining bundles in a unit cell need to be determined first. Fibers in each yarn bundle are packed parallel to each other. Most fibers used in composites have a circular cross section. When fibers are hexagonally packed, the maximum packing density is 0.9; if they are quadrilaterally packed, the packing density will not exceed 0.78. After consolidating, each yarn bundle can be considered as unidirectional composite. A tightly packed unidirectional composite normally has a fiber volume fraction (or packing density) ranging from 0.6 to 0.7. A tight 3-D woven composite will have a total fiber volume fraction of 0.4 to 0.6. Therefore, for design purpose, it is reasonable to assume that fiber bundles in 3-D orthogonal woven preforms and their composites have a packing density of about 0.65.

As it can be seen from Figure 2, warp spacing is defined by the distance D of two adjacent dents. Therefore, d_w in Figure 1 equals to D . If Z yarn size is smaller than that of warp yarn, then it can be assumed that the width W_y of warp fiber bundle is defined by R and that Z_y equals to e . Then, we have the following geometrical relations:

$$W_z = \frac{S_w}{p_f W_y} \quad (4)$$

$$Z_x = \frac{S_z}{p_f Z_y} \quad (5)$$

$$F_x = d_z - Z_x \quad (6)$$

$$F_z = \frac{S_f}{p_f F_x} \quad (7)$$

$$d_f = W_z + F_z \quad (8)$$

where S_w , S_f , and S_z are the same as those used in Equation (1); p_f is the packing density of fiber bundle; and W_y , W_z , Z_y , Z_x , F_x , F_z , d_z , and d_f are the sizes shown in Figure 1.

Therefore, for a 3-D orthogonal woven fabric with a given reed density, weft density, numbers of warp and weft layers, sizes of warp, weft, and Z yarns, the total thickness t and the total fiber volume fraction V_f as well as the dimensions defining the microstructure can be determined by Equations (2)-(8).

Figure 2. Warp spacing as affected by reed geometry.

As an example, fiber volume fractions and micro-structural dimensions of a 3-D orthogonal woven fabric having the following processing parameters is calculated below.

Material of fabric: Celion[®] G30-500 carbon fibers;

Sizes of yarns: warp yarn: 12K, $S_w = 0.449 \text{ mm}^2$, 5 layers;

weft yarn: 2x6K, $S_f = 0.449 \text{ mm}^2$, 6 layers;

Z yarn: 3K, $S_z = 0.11225 \text{ mm}^2$;

Reed density = 5.51 dents/cm (14 dents/in.), $D = 1.814 \text{ mm}$, $R = 1.397 \text{ mm}$, $e = 0.417 \text{ mm}$;

Pick density = 5.51 picks/cm (14 picks/in.);

Packing density of fiber bundles (assumed) = 0.65.

The results of the calculation are summarized below:

$W_y = 1.397$ mm, $Z_y = 0.417$ mm, $d_w = 1.814$ mm, $C_w = 0.223$,
 $Z_x = 0.414$ mm, $F_x = 1.40$ mm, $d_z = 1.814$ mm, $C_f = 0.273$,
 $F_z = 0.493$ mm, $W_z = 0.494$ mm, $d_f = 0.988$ mm, $C_z = 0.034$,
 $t = 5.43$ mm, $V_f = 0.535$.

The measured value of the total thickness of the fabric produced is 5.9 mm. Therefore, the predicted thickness is fairly close to the actual thickness. The difference between the calculated value and the measured value is probably caused by ignoring the thickness (h) of Z yarn segments on the surfaces of the preform.

Figure 3. Micrograph of the cross-sectional view of the composite (warp direction).

Figure 4. Micrograph of the cross-sectional view of the composite (weft direction).

After the preform was consolidated into composite, the thickness was reduced to 5.4 mm because of the compression during the consolidation process. Figures 3-4 are the micrographs of cross-sectional views of the composite. From these pictures, the micro-structural sizes can be measured (the micrographs have a magnification of 49.2x). The measured sizes are:

$$\begin{aligned} W_y &= 1.382 \text{ mm}, Z_y = 0.447 \text{ mm}, d_w = 1.829 \text{ mm}, \\ Z_x &= 0.386 \text{ mm}, F_x = 1.524 \text{ mm}, d_z = 1.91 \text{ mm}, \\ F_z &= 0.447 \text{ mm}, W_z = 0.467 \text{ mm}, d_f = 0.914 \text{ mm}, h = 0.18 \text{ mm}. \end{aligned}$$

It can be seen that the measured values are fairly close to those predicted. The thickness (h) of the Z yarn segments on the surfaces is about half of Z_x in this case. Based on the above measured sizes, the packing densities of fiber bundles in warp, weft, and Z directions were found to be 0.69, 0.66, 0.65 respectively, which are close to the assumed value.

4. RELATIONS BETWEEN FIBER VOLUME FRACTIONS AND Z YARN SIZE

Based on the equations developed above, the relations between fiber volume fractions and the thickness of Z yarn can be found. For a fabric with 12K Celion[®] carbon fibers as warp and 2x6K fibers as weft and having warp density of 5.51 ends/cm (14 ends/in.) and weft density of 4.72 picks/cm (12 picks/in.), the relations between fiber volume fractions as well as the empty pocket (resin rich pocket in composite) fraction and the size of Z yarn are plotted in Figures 5-6. It can be seen from Figure 5 that as Z yarn size increases, the total fiber volume fraction V_f decreases and the empty pocket volume fraction V_p increases. Figure 6 shows that as Z yarn size increases, the fiber volume fractions in warp and weft directions decrease sharply. With less fiber volume fractions in in-plane directions, in-plane mechanical properties are expected to be reduced. More resin pocket volume fraction leads to more voids and makes it easier to form cracks when the composite is subjected to load. Therefore, it is very important to have an appropriate amount of fiber reinforcement in the Z direction so as the composites will have optimum performance and meet the demands of the end use.

5. TENSILE MODULI OF 3-D WOVEN CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

After consolidation, each fiber bundle in the preform becomes a unidirectional composite. Therefore, 3-D orthogonal woven composites can be considered as composed of unidirectional composites in warp, weft, and Z directions and epoxy resin. The generic material properties of carbon/epoxy composite and epoxy resin are available in literature. They are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of generic carbon/epoxy composite and epoxy resin

	Generic carbon/epoxy [4]	Epoxy resin [5]
E_{11} (GPa)	134.0	3.45
E_{22} (GPa)	10.2	3.45
E_{33} (GPa)	10.2	3.45
ν_{12}	0.3	0.35
ν_{13}	0.3	0.35
ν_{23}	0.49	0.35
G_{12} (GPa)	5.52	1.28
G_{13} (GPa)	5.52	1.28
G_{23} (GPa)	3.43	1.28

Based on the material properties in Table 1 and the model shown in Figure 1 with the measured micro-structural sizes of composite, the effective moduli of the 3-D orthogonal woven composite can be determined by finite element method. COSMOSTM/M finite element system was used (solid element was applied) to predict the tensile moduli in warp and weft directions by applying

the boundary conditions: $u_x(x=0)=0$, $u_x(x=d_z)=0.01d_z$; $u_y(y=0)=0$, $u_y(y=d_w)=0.01d_w$. The results were $E_x = 53.1$ GPa and $E_y = 62.5$ GPa. The measured values for E_x and E_y were 55 GPa and 72 GPa [6] respectively. Comparing the predicted values to the measured ones, it can be seen that the finite element analysis, based on the measured structural parameters and the assumed material properties, generates reasonable results.

Figure 5. Total volume fractions of fibers(V_f) and empty pocket(V_p) versus Z yarn size.

Figure 6. Fiber volume fractions in warp(C_w), weft(C_f), and Z(C_z) directions versus Z yarn size.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A new method for predicting detailed structural parameters of 3-D orthogonal woven preforms and their composites has been developed. The example provided in this paper shows that the structural parameters predicted by this method were fairly close to the measured ones. This method is useful in the design of 3-D orthogonal woven preforms as well as in the mechanical analysis of

their composites. The relations between fiber volume fractions and Z yarn size show that the amount of fiber reinforcement in the Z direction plays a very important role in determining the fiber volume fractions and therefore the mechanical performance. A finite element model has been built up to predict the tensile moduli of composite and the predicted results were in good agreement to those measured.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported by NASA under Grant No. NAGW-1331 to the Mars Mission Research Center. The authors are grateful for this valuable support.

8. REFERENCES

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